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FRAMEWORK

Farmer Cluster Communication Guidelines

2022

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HELPING YOU GET

**SUPPORT
COLLABORATION
IMPACT!**

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Opportunity

Communicating the activity of your farmer cluster has many benefits

Internal Advantages

- Keeping cluster members up to date
- Motivating cluster members
- Encouraging knowledge exchange

External Advantages

- Finding existing networks and communication channels
- Sourcing additional support
- Building regional momentum and collaboration
- Advertising cluster businesses

In this *Communication Guidelines* document we want to share with you techniques and best practice examples, answering questions like:

- How can I use communications resources from initiatives, including Framework?
- How should I use social media?
- How can I get the most benefits for the least amount of time commitment?
- What are the audiences?
- Where can I reach them?
- And many more!

Alastair Simmons,
Dir. Taskscape Associates
Framework Communications
Knowledge Exchange &
Participation Partner

Successful Farmer Clusters reach out to communities and networks that can support their aims!

Communication is about storytelling, sharing the positive activity you're already doing!

Dr Niamh McHugh
Framework WP2 Lead
Head of Farmland Ecology
The Game & Wildlife
Conservation Trust

Sharing Knowledge

The Framework Project's Farmer Clusters were seeded from an existing UK network hosted by The Game and Wildlife Trust.

Looking at this network shows us ways Framework's clusters can communicate effectively...

Three pillars of communication:

Involve Organisations

- Involve as many useful Orgs and initiatives as possible around each cluster and the cluster network
- Try and create a diverse mix

Involve Communities

- Engage in outreach and collaboration with communities
- The UK network has found community events to be useful

Involve The Media

- Be aware of relevant media channels, reach out directly
- Use your **communities of communication** to build links
- UK clusters have appeared in local, national & international media - print, web + TV.

Develop community engagement steadily and carefully - but the people on your door step can be worth their weight in gold!

Jess Brooks
Cluster Advisor & Farmer
The Game & Wildlife
Conservation Trust

Communities of Communication

- Communities support and spread the word...
- Individuals bring their social media and useful contacts
- Sharing interest in local environments and issues...

They can *become advocates* for the cluster and businesses within it *building connections* including local links to orgs, initiatives and the media.

Strategy

Collaboration

A variety of people want to support and work with Farmer Clusters. Over the next decade, we'll all become even more concerned with sustainable productivity, tackling biodiversity loss and solving global heating through Agriculture.

So look out for:

- Orgs + initiatives seeking to benefit society (volunteering, engagement with sustainability etc.) .
- Media: Calls for content and topic coverage on cluster-related issues.
- Government: policymakers launching things and wanting to recognise progress.

Collaborators often have dedicated **communications staff and channels**, so seize **communication opportunities!**

Purpose

Whenever you're communicating about your Cluster – think about your purpose.

- Is it to **share information, news or positivity** with members and supporters?
- Is it to **raise the cluster's profile** to find new support?
- Is it to show **what's happening in your landscape?**

Link **communications purposes** with the right **channel** and **target audience** and you're heading for success!

Channels + Audiences

You have a message, activity, or event to share – so where to share it? Think about what **channels** to choose and what **audiences** you're engaging.

In general, use **traditional media channels** to reach specific audiences and **social media channels** to reach diverse actors + audiences.

Read on to see:

- Examples of traditional and social media use from the UK Farmer Cluster network
- How to map of audiences for your Farmer Cluster

Traditional Media

There are several ways to create impact using traditional media:

Target certain interest groups through your chosen communications channel.
eg. topic-based channels like news or programmes / publications on farming or the environment .

- Build awareness with existing audiences predisposed to welcome and support your clusters' efforts!
- Cultivate brand profile by being associated with existing high quality brands (established newspapers, magazines and broadcasters etc)

EXAMPLES	AUDIENCE
Newspapers + Magazines	Specific interest groups eg. farmers, environmentalists
Terrestrial + online television	Specific local or national audiences eg. local news. Topic programming
Local + national radio	Specific local or national audiences eg. local news. Topic programming

Examples

Newspaper / Magazine – local and national

National Radio + TV

In 2020 GWCT's Farmer Clusters were featured on **BBC Radio 4s Today programme**. In 2021 they invited **BBC Countryfile** to visit a cluster on the Hampshire – Dorset border to see farmer-led conservation agriculture work in action. In 2022, clusters in Kent were featured in Kent Wildlife's Magazine, **Wild Kent...**

FARMER CLUSTERS

CREATING A WILDER KENT

Farmer Clusters: Join our expanding farming team

MEET THE TEAM

Marc Crouch
Senior Farmer Cluster Officer (Darent Valley)
Marc is leading our farmer team in the Darent Valley and supporting the development of new clusters across the Kent Downs Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONB).

Suzanna Janes
Defra T&T Administrator
Suzanna comes from a farming family near Faversham and is supporting the delivery of the Defra Test & Trial. She joined the Trust after a successful career in horticulture and fresh produce supply chain compliance.

Alexa Murray Mutjahah
Marden & Tenterden Farmer Cluster Officer
Alexa is running the Defra Test & Trial to understand blended finance for nature-based solutions. She is supporting farmers in both Marden and Tenterden to get involved.

Lou Carpenter, Marden Farmer

Due to the impacts of the climate and nature crises, food security is an increasingly urgent issue. Therefore, our work with farmers is vital.

Formed of local farmers and land managers, our Farmer Clusters work together to share skills, experience and information about more sustainable approaches to farming and land stewardship. For example, some farmers have hosted farm walks to explain to the rest of the cluster what they are doing on their farm for wildlife.

By being in these clusters, farmers are keeping pace with a rapidly changing sector, engaging with their local communities and showcasing wildlife-friendly farming to the public.

"By working with Kent Wildlife Trust and our Farmer Cluster neighbours, with support from keen local naturalists who enjoy access to our wild areas, we're making gains for nature as well as helping to feed the nation."

Being part of a cluster also creates a one-stop-shop for organisations that

BBC Sign in Home News Sport Weather

one Countryfile

Home Episodes Clips Galleries @BBCCountryfile

Sorry, this episode is not currently available

Cranborne Chase

Matt Baker and Ellie Harrison uncover the wonders past and present of Cranborne Chase.

Matt unravels a puzzling piece of the area's past as he explores a 900-year-old mediaeval 'miz maze' hidden in the woods, before crossing the Chase to help tend to Britain's biggest modern day maze on the Longleat Estate. Ellie joins the UK's only 'supercluster' of farmers working together to encourage wildlife on their land. She also heads

Social Media

There are several ways to create impact using social media:

- Reach a broad audience of specialists and enthusiasts
- Get the most communications impact with the least time commitment by publishing quick posts about activity
- Include media like photos and video to boost engagement
- Humanise to boost engagement - introduce people and participants

EXAMPLES	AUDIENCE
Cluster Socials	Reach cluster participants, locals and enthusiasts
Collaborator Socials	Reach collaborators' participants and their networks
Local, national + international enthusiasts' socials	Reach people interested in cluster topics, and related initiatives

@MDSuperCluster
@FarmerCluster

Good examples:

notice how the Cluster is **tweeting about collaboration** - this went out on multiple collaborators' social media

notice how the Cluster is **linking to an award they received from another initiative**, supporting pollinators

notice how in this tweet, **including a short smartphone video** showing landscape change boosted likes and retweets

notice how the Cluster has a **good follower ratio**.

Cranborne Chase Farmer Cluster Retweeted

Martin Down Farmer Supercluster @MDSuperClust... · Oct 15, 2020

The season for many of our flowers and invertebrates is almost over... but you wouldn't think it looking at this scene! We've loved watching this little pocket of land develop over the last year. Pond, nectar mix, butterfly bank & new hedgerow all looking great [#farmingwithnature](#)

0:05 | 1,267 views

1 | 10 | 50

Martin Down Farmer Supercluster

889 Tweets

Martin Down Farmer Supercluster
@MDSuperCluster

Three Farmer Clusters surrounding Martin Down NNR and improving biodiversity, soil & water together.

Est. 2016...with an aim to last for generations!

Defra Bees' Needs Champions [farmerclusters.com/case-studies/m...](#)
Joined October 2019

372 Following 1,220 Followers

Tweets | Tweets & replies | Media

Martin Down Farmer Supercluster @MDSuperCluster ·
It's been a great two days at @NewForestShow.
@MeganRural has been flying the flag for #FarmerClusters and talking to the public about all the good work that the farmers are doing on the SuperCluster (and other Clusters/groups across the country too!)
[#LandscapeScaleConservation](#)

Jodie Case @JCaseNature · 27 Jul
Day two at the @NewForestShow has got off to a great start, and @Gameandwildlife staff are ready to rock 'n' roll!

sharing what's worked...

Farmer Cluster Communication Topics

learning from the above...

How to map...

Farmer Cluster Actors & Audiences

Step 1

List the interests and focus areas of your cluster...

For example, the *Aguilar de la Frontera* Cluster in Spain might list using biodiversity to:

- prevent desertification (erosion, water loss, poor soil health)
- Maintain olive yields over time
- Support pollinators, birdlife and game species

Step 2

Decide on a colour for local, regional and national.

This will help you colour code the actors + audiences you write onto your map.

Step 3

You're ready to map!

On the next page, write into the *venn diagram* the people, groups and organisations that you can think of who **share** the interests and focus areas of your cluster. Colour code them by *local, regional and national*.

Taking it further...

Bonus Activity

If you like:

1. add a colour for **international**
2. write around the edges of your venn diagram the factors interesting, motivating or affecting the people, organisations and initiatives you have listed...

eg. business considerations and opportunities, local issues, policy factors and regulatory compliance*

3. draw out a bigger diagram on a whiteboard for this exercise.

2. Examples

Many Agrifood businesses' consumers have increasing expectations for how outputs are meeting environmental and conservation sustainability targets – see an article discussing this [here](#).

Many countries and organisations are bringing in new environmental incentive schemes and regulatory frameworks shifting focus towards sustainable production – see [EU](#) and [UK](#) examples.

Mapping Actors & Audiences!

Need Inspiration?

Check out these maps of The Martin Down Super Cluster and Framework's Twitter followers...

Segments distribution

This graph shows the most relevant segments of your community. [Read more](#)

Top bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	18-24	27.91%
Gender	Male	62.38%
Country	United Kingdom	89.98%
Interests	Science	67.73%

ringer, naturalist

Actions ▾

Segment size

Distinctive bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	18-24	27.21%
Gender	Male	61.31%
Countries	United Kingdom	88.89%
Interests	Birds	76.6%

nfu, farming

Actions ▾

Segment size

Distinctive bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	18-24	32.73%
Gender	Male	61.23%
Countries	United Kingdom	95.38%
Interests	Science	67.76%

game, shooting

Actions ▾

Segment size

Distinctive bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	45-54	27.08%
Gender	Male	68.18%
Countries	United Kingdom	85.25%
Interests	Science	63.04%

Twitter Handles

The Martin Down Super Cluster
[@MDSuperCluster](#)
 The Framework Project
[@H2020_FRAMEwork](#)

It's the same offline...

+ for other communication channels...

Segments distribution

This graph shows the most relevant segments of your community. [Read more](#)

Top bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	18-24	26.10%
Gender	Male	61.21%
Country	United Kingdom	31.84%
Interests	Science	74.31%

farmer, farm

Actions

Segment size

Distinctive bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	18-24	27%
Gender	Male	70.34%
Countries	United Kingdom	85.25%
Interests	Science	70.89%

postdoc, services

Actions

Segment size

Distinctive bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	18-24	39.6%
Gender	Male	55.56%
Countries	Germany	18%
Interests	Science	82%

eu_h, project

Actions

Segment size

Distinctive bio keywords

Distinctive affinities

Top hashtags

Top characteristics

Age	18-24	54.42%
Gender	Male	65.22%
Countries	Germany	23.08%
Interests	Science	86.36%

Resources

for communicating

Tools

- Consider using a [social post scheduling platform](#) to enable collaboration and planning
- Consider using an accessible [online design platform](#) to design posts
- Many of these services have free plans and offer discounts for not-for-profit use

Techniques

- Find some good material on creating and serving communities with social media [here](#)
 - GWCT's UK Network can be explored [here](#)
 - Kent Wildlife Trust's Clusters can be explored [here](#)
 - The EU Partridge project also involved Farmer Clusters, explore more [here](#)
- investigate how individual clusters communicate!**

Context

55%

Internet traffic was on mobile in 2021

75%

Increase in searches for *nature friendly farming* since 2004

85%

Farmers use social media regularly

<https://explodingtopics.com/blog/mobile-internet-traffic>
<https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?date=all&q=nature%20friendly%20farming>
<https://www.hillsgreen.co.uk/blog/how-many-farmers-use-social-media/>

from the project

- The [project's legacy website](#) launches August 2022 and the **Info Hub** by January 2023 – explore the farmer cluster areas and useful resources
- **Discuss collaborating interest groups, orgs and initiatives with your Cluster Facilitator** – do they bring communications channels you can feature on?
- **Use Taskscape as a communications + knowledge exchange partner** on Framework – want professional photo or video coverage of some cluster activity? Talk to your Framework FCF, or reach out directly. We can collaborate with project partner organisations, hire media associates in your country or deploy ourselves, case by case.
- Want advice or analysis of your social media activity? Taskscape can help map your audiences
- **Let us know what you're up to** to have content featured or reposted on project socials.

Did you know?

Now that Framework's 11 clusters are rolling and we're in the next stage of the project communications plan Work Package 1 is providing **automatic activity forms** every three months for Cluster Facilitators.

By receiving information from the activity forms, the project can help support cluster communications!

WPI Web Chat

Approaches to communicating

Tone

- Look over your map of actors and audiences – what sort of communications tone will most engage them?
- Maybe it will be professional, positive, rough and ready activity posts from the field, or humour!
- Examine people communicating successfully in your interest areas and the tones that work for them
- Don't be afraid to test and and learn...

Test and Learn

- A test and learn approach to communications is important as it allows you to serve your audiences better and maximise the impact of the time and resources you have available
- Keep note of what content does well with which audiences you're trying to reach, this will make communicating easier and more impactful over time.

Values

Grass roots

Clusters are about **you**
– your circumstances!

Welcoming

Clusters are about **progress** – not certain movements or methods of agriculture

Open Minded

Clusters are about learning – **benefiting** from new thinking and opportunities

Coping with communication challenges...

Be ready for people bringing assumptions and agendas

When communicating about adopting more sustainable farming methods or valuing farmland biodiversity, it's hard not to be drawn into arenas of passionate debate about land use and land-based agriculture. The specifics will depend on your circumstances.

Consider having stock responses and resources ready share

Because farmer clusters often have businesses and initiatives involved from different approaches (different farming types or priorities) this can sometimes be confusing for the people you're communicating with. They may expect you to fit neatly into a box called 'conventional' 'organic', 'regenerative' or 'conservation'. This is particularly the case on social media, where people like to operate in tribes – because of this having material about your clusters' aims and activities ready to share can be useful.

Consider this example

A farmland biodiversity expert associated with one of the UK clusters was engaged on twitter in a discussion that progressed from combative to more discursive...

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Good luck cluster building!

Acknowledgements

We'd like to recognise the ongoing work of the Farmer Cluster facilitators and members across Framework. Have communications access points, resources or activity you'd like to share? Get in touch...

valuing farmland biodiversity

Prepared by Taskscape Associates

Photos copyright the Framework Project and named contributing partner

Thanks to GWCT & UK Farmer Clusters

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